

Leadership and Management Styles in Higher Education: Navigating the Everyday

Realities of Change

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In today's ever-evolving global landscape, the higher education sector has undergone unprecedented transformations. This dynamic necessitates universities to not only enhance cost efficiency but also to innovate in programme delivery. Today's leaders in higher education must be capable of managing change. This study focuses on how effective leaders are at managing change in higher education and, by association, what leadership styles they use. It also examines staff perceptions of how well their leaders manage change and which styles of leadership they think are most effective. This study will be an exploratory sequential design. The research problem will first be explored using qualitative methods because the sample is understudied. Qualitative findings will then be used to validate the questions in the quantitative survey instrument. This paper will highlight the methodology used and the ethical considerations of this study.

Keywords: Leadership styles, Managing Change, Higher Education, Staff Perceptions

Highlights

- This paper argues that due to demands for increased cost efficiency and innovation in programme delivery, higher education leaders must be capable of managing the associated unprecedented changes.
- This paper highlights the methodology used – an exploratory sequential design to examine how effective leaders are in managing change and by association what leadership styles they use.
- This paper concludes by examining the ethical considerations of this study.

Introduction

Higher Education institutions are increasingly expected to be more financially independent (Jones and Harvey, 2017), resulting in tensions among academics who feel their autonomy is being reduced and that, increasingly, managerialism is creeping in where the focus is on individual performance measures (Joyce and O'Boyle, 2013). The National Strategy for Higher Education (Hunt, 2011) identified the following challenges that the Higher Education sector is facing: increased numbers of students, the changing profile of students, increased unemployment and the changing nature of work which is increasing the emphasis on life-long learning and upskilling.

This research centred on how effective leaders are at managing change in higher education and what leadership styles they use. It also examined staff perceptions about how well their leaders manage change and which styles they believe most effective. The research method deployed was a sequential mixed methods design. According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) these methods provide numerous views of the phenomenon and therefore increase result credibility. Denscombe (2017) argues that it provides a fuller picture of the phenomenon being studied than that provided by a single approach. The research design consisted of semi-structured interviews and an on-line survey which were conducted with leaders and professional service staff within two university faculties. This paper provides an overview of the literature on change and leadership models, setting the context for the study before focusing on its methodological aims.

Change Management in Higher Education

Change describes 'any form of movement or transition from one state to another, from a common present to a future state' (Fox-Wolfgramm, Boal and Hunt, 1998, p. 87). Due to the changing nature of higher education, organisations need to place change management at the centre of their strategy (Ezzeddine *et al.*, 2023). There are numerous change management models, including one of the earliest models – the Kubler-Ross model (Kubler-Ross, 1969) which originated in psychology and outlines the emotional stages an individual experiences during bereavement or coping with a terminal illness. The Lewin model proposed that change involves three stages of unfreezing, the change and refreezing (Lewin, 1951). The Kotter model perceived change as a process (Kang *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, the Bridges model suggests the need to let go of the old to welcome the new beginning (Bridges, 2009). Other models examine change enablers such as the ADKAR (Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability and Reinforcement) model (Fry, 2021). Similarities exist in Lewin and Kotter models

of change management, both linear and effective for planned change. However, Kublar-Ross and Bridges address emotional stages that people experience during change without providing a formal change management plan as Lewin and Kotter suggest. The ADKAR model, concentrating on individual change, shares the focus on awareness of change with Lewin and Kotter but differs by omitting emotional considerations unlike the Bridges and Kublar-Ross models (Warrilow, 2024).

de Biasi (2019) argues that many change management approaches fail to consider the people side of things and their emotions (Buchanan, Claydon and Doyle, 1999). During change employees must discard the old way of doing things and gradually adapt to the new by adjusting their behaviour (Bridges, 2009), by creating an organisational environment that is conducive to change by developing high levels of commitment to the change through creating a climate of trust, shaping the conditions, organisational institutions (systems, structures and principles) and incentives (de Biasi, 2019).

Leadership Styles

Whilst leadership employ numerous styles in higher education, this study focused on three styles of transactional, transformational, and distributed leadership. Transactional leadership is often portrayed as ‘managerial leadership, which is strongly directive, motivating people with rewards in exchange for performance which meets expectations’ (Joyce and O’Boyle, 2013, p. 71). The main business of the university is conducted on a day-to-day basis using transactional leadership. Staff are motivated by setting goals (sometimes through the performance management scheme) and rewards (for example salary) are given for satisfactory performance. Transformational leaders motivate others by communicating organisational goals and inspiring staff to set aside their own needs for those of the organisation (Marks and Printy, 2003). The full range of leadership model (Bass, 1998) includes four styles of transformational leadership. These include charismatic leadership or idealised influence (leaders are admired and respected role models), inspirational motivation (motivating followers), intellectual stimulation (developing new ideas for ways to do things) and individualised consideration (focussing on developing others). The distributed leadership approach includes both leaders appointed to positions of authority and those recognised for their knowledge and expertise from different functions across the university, including academic and professional leaders (Gronn, 2011), and stakeholders (Jones, Harvey, and Lefoe, 2014b). It embraces both the notions of collegiality and autonomy and the need for management (Gosling, Bolden and Petrov, 2009).

Mixed Methods Research (MMR)

This study is using MMR which is defined as ‘an approach in which the investigator gathers both quantitative (closed ended) and qualitative (open ended) data, integrates the two, and then draws interpretations based on the combined strengths of both sets of data to understand research problems’ (Creswell, 2014, p.2). A pragmatic approach integrates methods into a single study (Creswell, 1995) and draws on the strengths of both approaches to better understand leadership styles in HE. This follows the philosophy that the research question should drive the methods used (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2005). Advantages of MMR include the provision of the opportunity to gain differing perspectives, firstly from the qualitative perspective and then quantitative perspective (Creswell, 2014). MMR can improve the sample by using different methods to recruit participants and ensuring the appropriate participants are included in the sample. By utilising both qualitative and quantitative data, this approach can enhance the data’s richness (Collins, Onwuegbuzie and Sutton, 2006).

Exploratory Sequential Design

This study is an exploratory sequential design see figure 1 below. The research problem will first be explored using qualitative methods because the sample is understudied. The methods include semi-structured interviews. Creswell & Poth (2016) identify a few basic characteristics of qualitative research including that the research is conducted in a natural setting where participants experience the issue that is being studied. ‘This up-close information gathered by actually talking directly to people and seeing them behave and act within their context is a major characteristic of qualitative research’ (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p. 182). The researcher is a key instrument in the research process, collecting data themselves through interviewing participants. Denscombe (2017, p. 231) argues that ‘research interviews focus on self-reports – what people say they do, what they say they believe and what opinions they say they have.’ Denscombe (2017) outlines several important interviewing skills for the researcher to demonstrate including sensitivity to the feelings of the interviewee, willingness to tolerate silences, using prompts to move the interview along and using probes to examine a topic in further detail. Other skills include confirmation with an interviewee that the researcher understands fully what they are saying and respecting when an interviewee may not wish to answer a question.

Figure 1: Exploratory Sequential Design. Adapted from (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 40).

After this exploratory stage, the qualitative findings will be used to confirm that the questions in the quantitative survey instrument are correct. Quantitative research methods comprised a cross-sectional survey where perceptions of leaders and staff are surveyed once. Survey questions will examine variables such as preferred style of leadership, training in change management and exploration of perceptions of leadership effectiveness to manage change using a 5-point Likert scale (Vagias, 2006). An online survey will be used as it is the most cost-efficient method and will increase the number of responses.

Research Questions

This research aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What leadership styles do leaders use to manage change in universities and how effective are these styles?
2. What are the staff perceptions about how well their leaders manage change and which styles they think would be most effective?

The following two hypotheses (and their null sets) will be examined:

H₀: Leaders who receive training in change management are not better equipped to manage change.

H₁: Leaders who receive training in change management are better equipped to manage change.

H₀: Those leaders who exhibit the characteristics of Distributed Leadership are not better equipped to manage change

H₁: Those leaders who exhibit the characteristics of Distributed Leadership are better equipped to manage change

Population, Sampling and Setting

The sample consists of academic and professional service leaders at the mid to senior level within two university faculties, to provide as broad a perspective as possible about leadership styles and change management within the faculties. Stratified sampling will be used where the sample will be divided into separate groups of academic leaders, professional leaders, academic staff, and professional services staff. The proposed sample size for the interviews is seventeen, including seven interviews within each faculty and three interviews with members of the senior management team to provide information about the context of where the research was conducted. It is proposed that all 370 staff across both faculties will receive the survey.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework for this study

Miles and Huberman (1994, p. 18) defined a conceptual framework as a visual or written product that ‘explains, either graphically or in narrative form, the main things to be studied – the key factors, concepts or variables and the presumed relationships among them.’ A conceptual framework is essentially a theory of what the researcher intends to investigate. Maxwell (2005) argued that a conceptual framework is something that the researcher creates (not pre-existing) and suggested four main sources of its development including the

researcher's experiential knowledge, theory and research, pilot or exploratory research undertaken and thought experiments.

The framework for this study is outlined in Figure 2 (see previous page) with a legend explaining how each part is laid out. Numbering shows the sequence in which to read the conceptual framework. Different coloured outlines differentiate between the context of the research and interpretation of the problem, which is real rather than assumed, assumptions made about the research and the planned research. This study focuses on leadership and management in HE, specifically within a university setting across two faculties. It aims to address the research gap regarding leadership styles and change management, positing that different styles such as transactional, transformational, distributed, and passive leadership impact the effectiveness of change management in this context.

Semi-Structured Interviews

Interview questions were developed around broad themes including types of everyday change, internal and external drivers of change, leading and managing change, leadership styles, resistance to change and organisational culture. These themes were chosen because of their relevance in answering the research questions. Denscombe (2017) emphasises the importance of building trust and rapport at the beginning of the interview. The initial question which asked the interviewee to describe their new role was designed to build rapport and to help the interviewee relax into the interview. Denscombe (2017) argues that the first question should offer the interviewee the opportunity to settle and relax. Twelve interview questions were developed and sent in advance to the leader/manager interviewees with ten questions sent in advance to staff interviewees. Interview questions were piloted with three university leaders/managers and staff initially to check they could be clearly understood and that the interview was the correct length. Research shows that a pilot study can result in the identification of any problems with the interview design allowing the design to be changed before the full-scale study commences (Brinkman and Kvale, 2018). In leading with interviews, the researcher used knowledge gained about the same to increase the sample size for the survey.

Survey

An online survey (using the DCU licensed survey tool Qualtrics) is being used to gather the perceptions of both leaders and staff about the effectiveness of leaders in managing change in higher education. The survey was adapted with permission from the Multifactor

Questionnaire (MLQ) (Bass and Avolio, 2004) and also adapted from the Distributed Leadership Inventory (Hulpia, Devos and Rosseel, 2009). The short survey comprises fifty questions which take a maximum of 15 minutes to complete. Forty-five questions from the MLQ were included in the questionnaire to measure transactional, transformational, and laissez-faire/passive leadership styles. Five additional questions were included that measured distributed leadership were adapted from the Distributed Leadership Inventory. The questionnaire consisted of a five-point Likert scale that ranged from not at all, once in a while, sometimes, fairly often and frequently.

Conducting interviews prior to surveys enabled the researcher to tailor survey questions effectively. There is no instrument available to measure leadership styles and change management, so the questionnaire was adapted from the MLQ because the MLQ has been used in numerous studies to measure transactional, transformational, and passive leadership styles (Bass and Avolio, 2004). It also provides an opportunity for staff to rate the effectiveness of their leaders. The survey will be piloted with three university leaders/managers and staff to check the reliability and validity of the survey, to verify that the questions could be clearly understood and that it is the correct length. Research suggests that pilot studies may give information about whether the study instruments used, such as a survey, are appropriate (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). Following this an updated survey will be sent to the full survey pool.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the institution's faculty ethics committee prior to the commencement of the research study. As there was a low level of risk with the research, it was not envisaged that there would be any risk to participants. However, to avoid the unlikely possibility that the research might cause some issues for participants, all participants were informed that they could withdraw at any time. Participants were also informed about the availability of the employee assistance service (EAS) and the support available from the Learning & Organisational Development unit. This was communicated to all participants through the participant information sheets and the email invitation to take part in the interview and survey.

Senior leadership at the university participated in interviews for qualitative data collection. To maintain anonymity, all interview data was pseudonymised with participants assigned pseudonyms at the start of the interview, in accordance with the said institution's ethical guidelines.

All survey information provided by participants was anonymous. The collection of IP addresses was disabled within the survey platform. Participants were advised to not include any identifying information within free text in the survey.

In line with the institutions ethics procedures a plain language statement was shared with all interviewees in advance, explaining the interview purpose and length, and that all interview data provided would be pseudonymised . Interviewee were also asked to complete an informed consent form in advance of completing the interview. An anonymous informed consent form was also included with each survey and participants were required to complete this before beginning the survey.

Conclusion

Higher education leaders need to be able to manage the unprecedented change in the university sector. There are numerous leadership styles they can use to manage change including transactional, transformational, and distributed leadership. There is a lack of research about how leaders manage change in higher education. This study uses an MMR approach and an exploratory sequential design to examine the following research questions: what leadership styles leaders use to manage change in universities and how effective are these styles. This research also examines staff perceptions about how well their leaders manage change and which styles they think most effective. Semi-structured interviews and an on-line survey are being used to explore these questions with leaders/managers and staff across two university faculties. Ethical considerations include informing participants they can withdraw from the study at any time, the availability of support from the employee assistance service, the anonymity of survey data and the pseudonymisation of interview data was essential due to the seniority of participants. The data gathered will be analysed using NVIVO and SPSS.

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